

Dealing with Weight Measurement Problems in Elevator Applications

Kurtuluş Erdem Bayraktar¹, Dağhan Atakay², Mehmet Selçok³, Berna Koca⁴, Tevfik Keleş⁵, Hamit Şıldır⁶ and Bayram Akdemir^{*7}

¹Electronic Engineering/Işık University, Istanbul

²Mechanical Engineering/Pamukkale University, Denizli

³Mechatronics Engineering/Sakarya University, Sakarya

⁴Electric Electronic Engineering/KTO Karatay University, Konya

⁵Electronics And Communications Engineering/Doğuş University, Istanbul

⁶Electric /Arel University, Istanbul

⁷Electric Electronic Engineering/Konya Technical University, Konya

(kurtulus.bayraktar@emlakkonutasansor.com.tr, daghan.atakay@emlakkonutasansor.com.tr,
mehmet.selcok@emlakkonutasansor.com.tr, berna.koca@emlakkonutasansor.com.tr, tevfik.keles@emlakkonutasansor.com.tr,
hamit.sildir@emlakkonutasansor.com.tr, *bakdemir@ktun.edu.tr) Email of the corresponding author

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Abstract – The Elevators are found in many areas of our lives. Elevators hold a special place in high-rise buildings, especially as vehicles for transporting people and cargo. Depending on the need, it's possible to find more than one type of elevator in the same building. Freight elevators and passenger elevators can vary in type depending on their speed and carrying capacity. However, one of the most important parameters in all applications is the load capacity of the elevator. Measuring the weight carried by an elevator is difficult due to factors such as its motion and exposure to vibration. This study addresses these weight measurement challenges and explores the fundamentals of designing a sensor resistant to these challenges. Applications are specifically targeted at vertically moving elevators. Accurately determining whether an elevator is empty, fully loaded, or overloaded is crucial for both the health of elevator traffic and its operational safety. Accurately measuring this parameter will prevent time, energy, and economic losses, thus extending the elevator's effective service life. In this study, gauss-based sensor is examined as weigh monitoring and evaluation to manage the elevator control.

Keywords – Elevator, Overload, Magnetic sensor, Loadcell, measuring weight

I. INTRODUCTION

The elevator is one of the most important load and human transportation vehicles of today. Especially vertical transporting has much importance in daily life. Skyscrapers, high-rise buildings and crowded places have many elevators that run non-stops. Generally, in these places have sophisticated elevator to manage the daily transporting traffic. one of the tricks to save time and energy is to measure the weight of the human that are inside the elevator cabin. In this study, two conventional methods and one magnetic-based sensor characterized for elevator are discussed. In elevator applications, there are 3 kinds of weight signals that can be expressed as fully load, over load and empty load (up to fully load).

Empty weight < Fully Load < Over Load

Elevators have a specific capacity. This capacity is usually expressed in kilograms and is called the rated load. The load on the car is constantly monitored to ensure safe system operation. Overloading and unbalanced load distribution both increase energy consumption and shorten the life of mechanical system components

Empty Load; The situation where there are no passengers or cargo in the elevator car and only the weight of the cabin and system components (cabin chassis, suspension, etc.) is called the empty load situation. Elevator system is designed with a counterweight of 40-50% of the nominal load, the system is not in balance when the car is empty. Since the counterweight is heavier, it tends to pull the car upwards. Therefore, the elevator motor displays a braking torque to prevent the upward connection of the counterweight when the elevator cabin moves down. During the elevator cabin goes up; The motor operates only to overcome friction losses and balance differences. Its energy consumption is low. On the contrary, during the elevator cabin goes down; As the counterweight pulls the cabin upwards, the motor applies a torque in opposite directions.

Under no-load conditions, the braking system and the speed control unit play a crucial role in maintaining safe and stable operation

Fully Load; The full-load condition represents the state in which the elevator car is loaded to its rated capacity with passengers and goods, as defined by the system specifications. The design ensures that the sum of the car weight and the rated load is approximately balanced by the counterweight together with the nominal load, in order to achieve optimal energy efficiency and smooth operation. The system is at its most efficient operating point; the engine is working only to overcome friction and acceleration losses. The braking system performs both motor speed control and safe stopping functions to ensure reliable and secure elevator operation. The control system regulates the elevator’s speed profile, including acceleration, constant speed, and deceleration phases.

Under full-load conditions, the system exhibits nominal energy consumption and operates at its highest efficiency level.

Over Load; An overload condition occurs when the elevator car is loaded beyond its rated capacity. Such a condition is considered hazardous as it may affect both safety and system performance. The motor torque requirement increases in order to overcome the additional load and maintain the desired speed.

In the elevator control system, the overload sensor, usually implemented as a pressure sensor or load cell mounted beneath the car platform, monitors the load condition. When the measured load exceeds the defined threshold (typically 110% of the rated load), the sensor activates an overload signal within the control circuit. The doors remain open, or if closed, the elevator does not receive a movement command. An audible and visual “Overload Warning” is triggered. Passengers are advised to remove excess load so that the total weight does not exceed the rated capacity. From an energy standpoint, operating the motor under overload conditions may cause an increase in current, elevated temperatures, and the engagement of protective devices to prevent damage.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

In elevator applications there are three weigh monitoring methods to evaluate the moving. In order to evaluate the elevator cabin load, there are three sections of cabin load to be needed to explain. 1000kg cabin capacity of an elevator loading profile explained in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Understanding elevator weigh with a switch.

Up to 1000kg, (green area), is normal situation of the cabin load. In this case, elevator obeys any call command. In yellow section, limit of the loading capacity is indicated a signal called “full load” [1-2]. this signal has meaning as elevator is full and any more elevator doesn’t stop any floor level up to decrease the load level. Thus, the elevator does not stop at any floor until the weight inside decreases. Full load signal has important meaning in Elevator traffic management algorithm to gain time and energy saving.

Switched Method: First method to generate load signal is so primitive, simple and cheap. This method includes one switch to understand the signal and gives logical signal as “on” or “off” [3]. Figure 2 shows the use of a simple switch to detect the elevator weight.

Figure 2. Understanding elevator weight switch.

Obtained signal has only two meanings. Elevator is normal or not. Figure. 1 gives only one signal to evaluate. Figure 1a means elevator is empty and Figure 1b means elevator is overload. Figure 1c is output signal for elevator control board. From Figure 1c, elevator is full signal coded as “2” has not been seen. Figure 1d shows classical switch for any elevator application.

Loadcell is generic weight measurement device [4,5]. Loadcell based on material strength and gives analogue signal. Loadcell signal must be amplified by instrumentation amplifier [6,7].

Load Cell Method: Load cells installed on the car or counterweight measure the load accurately and convert it into analog or digital signals. Allows continuous monitoring and provides precise measurement. It is more expensive and more complex to install than other methods. Moreover, in order to measure any cabin weight, four pieces are needed. From Figure 3b, output of the loadcell is analogue and continuous. It is possible to understand there kinds of signal as elevator normal, full and overload respectively.

Figure 3. Understanding elevator weigh with a switch.

Pressure From Figure 3c, there are 4 pieces loadcell to measure. And cabin is connected to these loadcells. In case of any emergency stopping forces loadcells. During the forced stopping, loadcell can lose their calibrated values [8,9]. So, in future maintenance cost are high. But for precision measuring is good way. Loadcell uses strain Guage sensor structure inside. Strain gauge includes strainable wire-based resistors inside and in case of any strength, wires stretch thus increase the R value. the resistivity change that occurs is interpreted. But strain gauge must be controlled regularly in case of damaged calibration [10,11].

Magnetic Displacement Method: Sensors, often installed under the cabin floor, detect the weight inside the elevator car. Provides direct load measurement and may require one sensor. During the loading, cabin carrier rubber wedges flex. This flexing may lead to change in distance between magnet and sensor. So, this change in the set gap gives the weight value. Figure 4 shows magnetic displacement sensor method.

Figure 4. Magnetic displacement sensor-based measuring.

Figure 4a shows the rubber blocks flexing during the load of the elevator. Figure 3b gives linear changing like loadcell output ability. Figure 3c shows designed sensor and one magnet. One of the most important features here is that the sensor works touchless. Thus, it is not affected by the physical hard stops of the elevator.

On the contrary, touchless working brings an obstacle. The biggest problem is to find how can be calibrated for different kinds rubber. In order to solve this problem, there is a circuit used. This answer also forms the main basis of the user manual. Figure 4a shows empty cabin voltage. There are two points are needed. First point can be obtained during the cabin is empty.

Figure 5a shows 2.2Volts. Later, cabin will be loaded determined load such as 250kg. Thus, second measured point can be obtained. Figure 5b shows loaded cabin voltage as 2.5Volts after 250kg.

Figure 5. Magnetic displacement sensor calibration

With two points show as 2.2 Volts equal to 0 kg and 2.5 Volts is 250kg. Figure 6 shows mathematical expression of the obtained values.

$$x_1=2.2$$

$$x_2=2.5$$

$$y_1=0$$

$$y_2=250$$

y axis indicates kg and x axis indicates volts. A and B are intersections points. Alpha angle indicates the slope between x axis and drawn line. Alpha has linear correlation with slope and indicates as “m” in math.

Figure 6. Linear line equation

Linear line equation with two known points is shown Equation 1.

$$\frac{y - y_1}{y_2 - y_1} = \frac{x - x_1}{x_2 - x_1} \tag{1}$$

From Equation 1, filled the known parameters, linear equation obtained as Equation 2 shown as below.

$$y = 833.33333x - 1833.3333 \tag{2}$$

For the cross check; x=2.2 Volts y=0 and display show 0 at hand display. On the other hand, 2.5 volts can be meant as 250 kg. simple reverse engineering can be executed from Equation 2. 1000 kg over load signal can be occur at;

$$1000kg = 833.33333x - 1833.3333$$

$$x = (1000 + 1833.3)/833.33$$

$$x = 3.4 \text{ Volts}$$

Thus, overload point can be programmed as 3.4 Volts. Now after evaluated the voltages level, Figure 1 can be arranged as Figure 6. According to Figure 7, 3.4 volts shows full load of the cabin.

Figure 7. Final evaluated voltages level for cabin load.

For overload point, 3.519 Volts can be calculated from Equation 2 regarding 110% payload. After all calculated points and obtained linear lines. Errors centered;

III. RESULTS

In this study, magnetic displacement-based sensor specialized and compared the other weight measurement methods in elevator industry. Especially, easy installing, economical benefit and touchless measuring are benefit of this application. For different elevator styles, simple calibration method is explained and presented its tricks. Magnetic displacement-based sensor uses linear equation to create simple solution. In order to adaptation of the sensor two points known linear line equation is used. New method just has one magnet and one sensor. Because of the two points approximation, magnet force known as gauss not affect the installation style.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study, magnetic displacement sensor-based elevator weight measuring sensor is explained and it has been development calibration method based on two points known linear equation. In this concept just include one magnet and linear analogue output sensor. Obtained equation has linear characteristic on determined points and applicable for different type elevators such as hydraulic, double speed and VVVF.

V. CONCLUSION

Elevator industry uses weight measuring components. Simple one has just a switch. These means elevator normal or not. This method is cheap. Another method has four loadcell to understand cabin load. It is good resolution but has some disadvantages. It needs calibration regularly, and in case emergency stopping of elevator can be lost measuring ability. But explain method measures touchless and easy to instal and calibration. It merges cheap one's conveniences and loadcell abilities in same structure. According to simplicity, discussed simple calibration method. Two points known linear equation is configured for this application to obtain linear approximation.

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